
Teaching resources used in the classroom for visualization

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Abstract

This article discusses a proposal for a pedagogical resource that uses security cameras, facilitating hands-on experience with objects and materials to develop visualization through an image-based inclusion process. The learning process of introductory studies, the orthogonal projective system, and constituent elements (point, line, and plane) was studied in Descriptive Geometry by students aged 14 to 17 in high school technical training programs. Learning to see is an open possibility in this proposal for understanding the formation of projections and resuming the practice of observation. Three-dimensional visualization fosters recognition of the rendered image. Integration with objects and the generation of images using the main aspects of projective drawing contribute to enhancing the workflow and improving the understanding of geometric concepts.

Keywords: Projective system. Orthographic views. Cameras. High school.

Didactic resources applied in a classroom for visualization

Resumo

Este artigo discute uma proposta para recurso pedagógico que utiliza câmeras de segurança, favorecendo uma experiência de manipulação de objetos e materiais para o desenvolvimento da visualização em um processo de inclusão pela imagem. O processo de aprendizagem dos estudos introdutórios, do sistema projetivo ortogonal e de elementos constituintes (ponto, reta e plano), foram estudados em Geometria Descritiva por alunos da faixa etária de 14 a 17 anos, do Ensino Médio de cursos de formação técnica. Aprender a ver é uma possibilidade aberta nessa proposta para entendimento da formação das projeções e retomar a prática de observação. A visualização em três dimensões gera reconhecimento da imagem realizada. A integração com objetos e a geração de imagens com os aspectos principais do desenho projetivo favorecem o incremento da rotina dos trabalhos e melhor entendimento dos conceitos de geometria.

Palavras-chave: Sistema projetivo. Vistas ortográficas. Câmeras. Ensino Médio.

Introduction

Geometry arises from the observation of phenomena linked to processes of representation or forms of construction using specific instruments. In the approach to this discipline, there is a tendency toward rationalization to support mathematical reasoning, stripping it of its experimental

¹Translated by Joab da Silva Lima. Professor at the Federal Institute of Acre (IFAC). Holds a Master's degree in Education from the Federal University of Rondônia (UNIR).

and observational nature. The contribution of this article is to reflect on and study theory through experimentation, sharing a method developed and implemented through in-person activities linked to the practice of manual drawing (OLIVEIRA, 2016).

Using security cameras outside their usual context for educational purposes is a relevant objective for drawing exercises, serving as a classroom practice to observe and develop visualization skills. Figure 1 presents a representation to aid in understanding the concepts of projection, the projection of planes onto a horizontal plane, and the Épura¹.

Figure 1 – Épura: projection of the vertical plane onto the horizontal

Source: Prepared by the author.

Visualization is a process developed throughout one’s academic life, from elementary school through college. It is not exclusive to activities involving geometry, since, according to Veloso (1998), it is:

- A cognitive process involving investigative activities;
- Reasoning that refines visual perception beyond mere observation;
- Born from the manipulation of models and materials, reinforcing and building a memory of images to support complex activities based on these experiences.

Thus, learning visualization begins with the evocation of memories arising from the student’s daily life or imagination in constructing situations for problem-solving, not exclusively in mathematics.

Experience, experiment, and lived experience are three very similar words. “If the experiment is repeatable, the experience is unrepeatable; there is always something like the first time” (LARROSA, 2002, p.

¹ Épura—a word derived from the Greek *επουρος* /epouros/—means “driven by favorable winds; favorable” (MALHADAS, 2007), that is, the vertical plane projected onto the horizontal. The dihedral is a space bounded by two planes (vertical and horizontal); the method of dihedral projection was named Épura by Gaspard Monge in the 18th century.

28). Classroom practice, as a phenomenon in itself, involves using a technological tool not for the technology's sake, but to achieve or transform outcomes in learners. We aim to provide the experience and empower young people to take the lead as knowledge builders.

Classroom practice: interaction and engagement.

Of the works developed by the GEPETICEM² at UFRRJ, two served as the basis for this research: the book by Marques and Bairral (2014) and the dissertation by Izar (2014), works by professionals concerned with offering their audience the possibility of participating in the construction of knowledge, of students moving beyond the role of mere spectators and taking the lead in the development of scientific production. Thus, it does not matter what the characteristics or age of the technology used are, but rather how it is used—that can be the great discovery.

Izar (2014) emphasizes the importance of the evolution of education and the advancement of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT), whether in face-to-face or distance learning settings, with resources to add appeal and dynamism to the teaching-learning process. His work on Homothety uses the manual pantograph and computer technology, develops hands-on activities, and extends into the digital world (IZAR, 2016). He highlights in his work the complexity of a group of students and works by considering Vygotsky's concept of the Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD). Beyond the possibilities, one must consider the capacity to receive and the potential for interaction to occur, “[...] for each child's ZPD changes as content is presented. It is a constant process (IZAR, 2014, p. 29).”

The concrete actions of each student depend on the form and nature of the elements provided by the teacher. The choice depends on the degree of proximity between the teacher's world and that of their students, on the mediating element. Izar (2014), in choosing the theory developed by Vygotsky as the basis for her work, seeks to observe how the external environment can foster the development of knowledge. He also draws on the concept of visual culture to guide his choices.

The work of Marques and Bairral (2014) complements this intention and piques our interest in the way the authors combine the concepts of Bakhtin and Vygotsky, from the interest in communicating and observing how discourse is constructed and its meanings, to the path toward reaching the other. From our constitution, we use the fragments cited by Skliar (2012), valuing our constitution for its diversity and multiplicity.

² GEPETICEM – Study and Research Group on Information and Communication Technologies in Mathematics Education – developed the Online Educational Curriculum Materials (MCEO) project led by Professor Dr. Marcelo Bairral of UFRRJ

Marques and Bairral (2014) propose the use of a stigmatized device in mathematics classes—the calculator—not as a mechanism, but as a tool to foster the development of mathematical reasoning, through an analysis of the school context and its appropriation of technological resources, the barriers, and proposals for advancement in a field that shapes citizens. In this study, security cameras, even when not connected to the network, function as a device in which the images generated on the monitor serve as a mediator between the components of the communication system.

Development Research - *Design-Based Research* (DBR)

Conducting research in the classroom itself requires the teacher to keep an eye on the class routine while maintaining a degree of detachment to analyze the results of their practice. It would be a mistake to imagine it is possible to split oneself in two. When choosing the methodology for this research, we opted for development research or *Design-Based Research* (DBR), as it involves the construction of an application, its implementation, and results in the classroom. A way to conduct the research by looking at the situation from within.

The ongoing process of acquiring, assembling, testing, applying, and reflecting on results—with a focus on the student and support for learning—constitutes the basic steps of the path to follow. This approach avoids relying on a pre-packaged solution or a rigid, fixed strategy, and instead embraces a process characterized by cyclical and continuous stages. Cyclical, not because it returns to the initial starting point, but because it fosters a new refinement, a more pleasant form that aids in the mental visualization built with the support of physical resources.

The purpose of a DBR is to apply and solve a problem detected through a practice that is tested and reformulated cyclically throughout the course of the practice. It is an interpretive perspective that continuously articulates theory and practice in educational research with a focus on learning. Even after the research period has ended, it does not remain closed; that is, its proposal leaves an evolutionary path open to contributions from other segments complementary to the study. In summary, a DBR is based on the following principles (BROWN, 1992; COBB et al., 2003):

- A cyclical process of implementation, observation, analysis, and generation of results;
- A constant focus on learning, through an intervention that can be constantly reformulated; and
- A dynamic of interpretation and theory generation situated within the complex context in which it emerges.

Collins et al. (2004) describe that, with DBR, one can address questions relevant to the context of the research being conducted. These questions are addressed according to the needs of the theoretical framework. The authors also highlight the role of formative assessment to be observed throughout the process. The environment built around the application makes young people feel more at ease to experiment and reinforce learning points. Learning occurs through a routine that fosters observation, experimentation, and reinforcement of the topic being studied. DBR is well-suited for education due to the scope of its application, as observation tools can be diverse and well-adapted to the object of study.

Security cameras, visual prostheses³

Technical Drawing is responsible for introducing students to the language of graphic representation. The device is not a programming language nor is it an existing drawing application. Its purpose is to facilitate visualization and serve as a bridge for communication between the teacher and the student.

During the study, the need was observed for a system to replace the observer's viewpoint in order to explore the concepts of technical drawing, for the understanding of the systematization of the representation of the main orthographic views of a part or model.

The camera system operates with a central unit that receives images from cameras connected via coaxial cables. The choice was made for the simplest, lowest-cost model, without a protective dome and featuring a 2.5mm lens with an 89° field of view. In Figure 2, we present the relationship between the lens angle and the coverage of its field of view.

Figure 2 – Lens Types

Source: Available at: <<http://www.protecnos.com.br/artigos/escolha-de-lentes-para-cameras-cftv/>>
Accessed on: Mar. 6, 2015.

We invested in a process of trial and error, as the method itself dictates. On the monitor, it was possible to monitor and verify whether the set of generated images was

³ Bolite-Frant and Castro (2001) employ the concept of a prosthesis for an object or piece of equipment used as an extension of the body, enhancing its functions rather than as an object to compensate for a physical limitation or an aesthetic aspect.

corresponding to the position and dimensions. The images do not have the appearance of a cylindrical projection but exhibit a distortion similar to that of a conical projection, resembling the appearance of our vision. Another topic that can be addressed and resolved through this research is the comparison of projection types using a parallel-cylindrical light source and a point-conical light source (Figure 3).

Figure 3 – Reference of projection types

Source: Prepared by the author.

Proposals, tasks, activities

The proposed research process consists of a set of practices that begin with the exploration of basic concepts of spatial geometry. The manipulation of objects and the identification of their elements, a preparation that ranges from experience with three-dimensional objects to their two-dimensional representation. The construction of images so that memory based on experimentation can be evoked when necessary, and even before representation on paper, images generated by cameras were introduced as visual aids, a bridge between the object and the figure on the monitor screen. In Table 1, we outline the sequence of steps and the materials used according to their proposals.

Table 1 – Summary of implementation and application steps

STAGES	MATERIAL/RESOURCES	PROPOSAL
1	Reused product packaging	Exploration and identification of the components of prismatic solids
2	Reused product packaging	Flattening of prisms
3	Cameras and packaging	Identification and sketching of orthographic views
4	Cameras, miniatures, and wooden models	Identification and sketching of orthographic views
5	Cameras and plans with colored EVA foam	Study of point coordinates
6	Typical parts for technical drawing study	Final drawing with the aid of instruments
7	Acrylic cube with LED strips	Investigate the projections of lines and their projections onto the first dihedral

Source: Prepared by the author.

The first stage focused on manipulating the object and naming the elements of a prismatic solid. Product packaging was provided to each student, who was also required to fill out a worksheet with their conclusions (Figure 4), as well as identify the number of vertices, edges, and faces of each box, along with their dimensions expressed in centimeters and millimeters (Figure 5). The objective was to start with an everyday object, as found on store shelves, and investigate its main face and the communication resources used—color, font, and information—that is, to familiarize students with how to represent shapes through observation of the model.

Figure 4 - Boxes used as models

Source: Author's photo collection.

Figure 5 – Analysis of volumetric composition

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Investigação:

- a. Planos 12 planos
- b. Arestas 24 arestas
- c. Vértices 48 vértices
- d. Dimensões 3 dimensões

Representação:

Source: Digital research archive.

The flattening of the box promotes an understanding of the volume and the positions of the faces in the solid's composition, through the process of disassembling and reassembling it, reproducing it in another material, and applying the concept of scale reduction to create a smaller model (Figure 6). These, therefore, were the activities of the second stage that aided in the construction of memory, which were evoked in subsequent exercises.

Figure 6 – Cut-out packaging for flattening

Source: Author's photo collection.

The first setup and interaction with the device took place in the third stage (Figure 7). The surprise of encountering the equipment, the curiosity about how it works, and the type of activity to be carried out, changes the atmosphere of a traditional class. Students behave like researchers trying to figure out what will happen. This is important so that the teacher does not impose a different activity and fall into a conventional pattern of exploration. The equipment dominates the classroom setting, making it resemble a laboratory or a film set.

Figure 7 – Observation of the model with a Styrofoam background

Source: Author's photo collection.

This class followed a routine of explaining the new content with the presentation of the first concepts of projective drawing for graphic representation (Figure 8). At first, the teacher holds a package in front of the cameras to present them as visual aids, assuming the observer's position, and then assembles a set with more boxes, which is later altered by the students. As an introductory exercise, a higher pace of drawing production was observed compared to traditional classes, both in the execution of sketches and in the proposal of new arrangements.

Figure 8 – Activity carried out in the class depicted in Figure 8

Source: Author's digital archive.

To reinforce the observer's positioning relative to the objects in the first dihedral and the correspondence of orthographic views, the fourth stage uses toys and miniatures, employing a playful approach to explore positional relationships (front/back; high/low; left/right). In this stage, reproductions of the images were used to create collages (Figure 9). Subsequent classes, featuring more detailed objects, served as a reference for creating sketches of the parts.

Figure 9 – Reproduction of the material distributed to students

Source: Author's digital collection.

The fifth stage focused on the study of the coordinates of a point and its location in the projection trihedron (Figure 10). At each stage or session of using the set, changes were made, and elements were added or removed according to the students' performance and suggestions. It was not the objective of the research to present a definitive configuration, but rather a set capable of receiving contributions from its users.

Figure 10 – Reproduction of the material distributed to students regarding the representation of the coordinates of the point in space

Source: Prepared by the author.

There were changes in the backgrounds, alterations to the camera mounts, and proposals for new objects and activities (Figures 11 and 12). In this stage, the theoretical content of point coordinates and their projections was studied, but with the visual foundation of the observations made previously. The terms:

- Abscissa (AB): Position marked on the ground line with a zero point as a reference;
- Offset (AF): Distance between the point and the vertical plane;
- Elevation (CO): Height of the point relative to the horizontal plane.
- (P) [AB; AF; CO]

Figure 11 – Smaller supports with metal tubes and a wooden base. Cardboard planes covered with EVA: horizontal plane (orange); vertical plane (purple); and profile plane (pink)

Source: Author's photo collection.

Figure 12 – System assembled in the third application

Source: Author's photo collection.

The sixth stage consisted of a transition and review of the concepts studied for application in technical drawing. Traditional models are often used without reference to a specific application, but the students made references to previously studied objects, such as the mannequin, the Rubik's Cube, and the stairs formed by the boxes (Figure 13).

Figure 13 – Models used for the sketching exercise

Source: Author's photo archive.

The study of inclined plane projections associated with the review of point coordinates is presented in Figure 14. In the next step, we will examine the details and labeling of line projections with the aid of the acrylic cube with LED strips.

Figure 14 – Activity sheet with orthogonal and isometric grids

Source: Digital research archive.

The research proposal was to reverse the traditional order of GD instruction, which begins with the study of point projection and moves to the study of solids. By observing the projections of solids in the first dihedral, students constructed a reference for understanding the constituent elements of volumes and demonstrated ease in solving new problems presented with greater complexity.

Many questions are answered by classmates with a keener understanding; thus, the investigation flows more naturally. New concepts are incorporated more easily, for example, the visualization of coordinates through their identification on the dihedral model (Figures 15 and 16). The names present a difficulty in assimilation, with the exception of “distance,” which has a more familiar meaning.

Figure 15 – Experimentation and identification of the positions of the lines by a student

Source: Author's photo collection.

Figure 16 – Activity involving line projections using a cube with LED strips

Source: Digital research archive.

In 2014, without the app's support, understanding the projection of the dihedral planes to form the sketch took longer. Grasping how the projection was formed on the plane, despite the use of the projected image as a shadow, required a slower assimilation process. Furthermore, the connection between the concepts of projective drawing—the two-dimensional representation of a three-dimensional object—became more complicated. The use of images of moving models and the simultaneous generation of the projection diagram significantly improved

production of the exercises. For the first class, the objective of creating the *Épura* for four sets of packaging was achieved.

The decision to use product boxes as models guided our modification of the system, taking advantage of their visual compositional elements such as: typeface; shapes used on the box; and identification of the box's main aspect based on its display position on the shelf. The main change in this phase was switching the projection surfaces to white opaque polystyrene sheets, with the aim of making the model stand out more through the contrast between figure and background. The objects became more prominent, their volume was better perceived, and the image quality on the monitor improved. The students also developed a habit of consulting the image on the monitor to use it as a reference for their drawing, identifying the mediation (VIGOTSKI, 1998; 2008) being performed by the equipment—that is, the student establishing a connection between their reasoning and the proposed problem without the teacher's interference or assistance. The clues or shortcuts observed in the process described by Vygotsky go beyond the teacher's role as mediator, with the student assuming the leading role in solving the exercise.

The aim is to associate orthographic views with the study of scales and apply the study of meso- and macro-space (GIMENEZ; FORTUNY, 1998⁴, *cited in* BAIRRAL, 2012) as a continuation of this work.

Final Considerations

This article presented a device developed to facilitate experiences based on the visual and manipulative exploration of models in the construction of visualization, in-person activities linked to the practice of manual drawing with a focus on the development of spatial reasoning and visualization⁵.

An application of this nature contributes to the development of other processes linked to visualization, making them important for all individuals, such as: description, representation, orientation, and communication. The study may contribute to the scientific community by:

- Developing and applying a practice to cultivate an intuitive visual approach, in order to facilitate the learning of Descriptive Geometry concepts and to aid in the visualization of the trihedral system and its projections.

⁴ GIMÉNEZ, J.; FORTUNY, J. M. **Praxis Guides for Secondary School Teachers. Mathematics: Content, Activities, and Resources**. Barcelona: Praxis, 1998. Insert the primary reference here.

⁵ Educational curriculum materials resulting from this research are currently being finalized for publication at <http://www.gepeticem.ufrj.br/portal/categoria/materiais-curriculares/>

- Experiment with changes in the arrangement of sets of solids or the positions of objects in the projection trihedron to explore proportional relationships.

It is possible to observe, throughout the activities implemented and analyzed, through students' comments and the exchange of opinions with teachers, the ease of visualizing the views and the discussion generated based on the images. During the sessions, a difference in the classroom routine facilitated by the system was noted. In 2014, during the initial GD classes, using small wooden pieces or product boxes manipulated in front of the class, the group—usually consisting of 15 to 20 students—gathered around the table, and it was impossible to ensure that every student had the same vantage point for understanding orthogonal projection. Even with the support of illustrations depicting the projection of solids onto planes, a recurring pattern of solutions led to repetitive exercises without reflection. The difference in this application lies in the camera, which acts as the observer's eye. The image generated on the monitor—colorful and close to observed reality—facilitates a faster understanding of the projections.

The implementations that took place after the applications in regular classes confirmed the equipment's effectiveness. There was an integration of viewpoints and the construction of a plausible basis for the discussion on visualization. The discussion, based on printed images referencing three-dimensionality without first establishing the concept of spatiality, did not trigger a recall of memory or references from the students' repertoire of experience. The role of the projections—the superimposition of points in orthographic views—became clearer through the discussion of the images generated by the device and the discussion initiated by the students. Even though the images generated by the cameras exhibited distortion due to the type of lens, bringing the image closer to conical vision, this was quickly compensated for in the interpretation of the orthographic views.

There was a significant gain from the observations of the session participants. Notable observations included the quality of the projection planes and the figure-ground relationship, as well as control of object lighting; furthermore, the suggestion to produce the projection using a single light source—a flashlight—to highlight the object's projection on the planes was noted.

The assertiveness of the research direction, using the transparent methodology of the DBR, transformed the application and its resulting practices into a transformable object of study, up to the present moment, conferring a characteristic of non-imposition of technology on the practice of dialogue within the class or workshop groups, valuing the interaction among participants and the discussion provoked for an effective construction of knowledge.

The possibilities for changes, adaptations, and proposals regarding the use of security cameras for the study and design of visualization are not exhausted. The concepts developed by Vygotsky were observed, such as mediation—whether through the mechanism or through the interaction among

people, the construction of knowledge through the exchange of experiences in the social environment, the realization of the zone of proximal development, and the balance among group participants.

Further studies could explore aspects of visualization, the ways of approaching it, and how people internalize these images. Questions to be investigated in a study more dedicated to this topic—delving deeper into our goal of creating an application that generates a shared visualization—could raise inquiries about how each observer’s mental images are formed after experimenting with the mechanism.

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